

SUMMARY

THE CENTENARY CELEBRATIONS OF THE INSTITUTE OF CHARTERED ACCOUNTANTS OF SCOTLAND

by *A. L. de Bruyne*

After having given a short summary of the festivities on the occasion of the Centenary (about which he reported more in detail in the August 1954 issue of „de Accountant”) the author gives a short outline of the history of the accountancy profession in Scotland with the help of the book: „A History of the Chartered Accountants of Scotland from the earliest times to 1954.”

About 1700 already auditing was performed by book-keepers as a free profession.

But the accountancy-profession not only developed from the book-keeper's work: Accountants were appointed by the Courts to prepare a scheme of ranking and division for submission to the Court in bankruptcy cases, whilst the development of commerce and industry in the eighteenth and nineteenth century made it necessary to get the assistance of experts who had a considerable mercantile skill.

Then the author gives a sketch of the development of the Scottish accountancy bodies and asks attention for the training. The Scottish Institute is one of the few organisations who, just as the Netherlands Institute of Accountants, provide tutorial classes.

At the beginning of 1954 1918 students had been registered with the Scottish Institute.

In the course of the years a co-operation developed between the profession and the Universities. For some branches of study attendance at University classes is compulsory.

The author then gives a survey of the examination syllabus and in this connection points out the desire of some to organise a long period of academic study, coupled with a series of attachments from time to time in industrial establishments and professional offices.

Finally the author sums up some thoughts of the lecture of Ian T. Morrow „The Accountant in modern society”, o.a. his suggestion that the profession may have to decide whether it is going to follow other professions in creating specialists in the different fields, or whether it will continue to be satisfied with providing the basic training only.